

Anaerobic digestion of biowastes for sustainable agriculture

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ABSTRACT

Anaerobic bio digestion technology has recently gained attraction due to its ecological benefits of the utilization of both animal and agricultural wastes, besides, helping in conserving natural resources and minimizing pollution. The non-commercial energy sources such as cattle dung, crop residue, forest waste and firewood contributed more than 89 per cent of energy consumed in rural households with extremely poor heat conversion efficiency of about 8-10%. This ultimately leads to atmospheric pollution during its burning and on the other side, high dependence on firewood may pave the way for deforestation. The biogas produced through anaerobic digestion of biowastes by micro-organisms offers an appropriate technique to convert non-conventional energy into conventional energy. In particular, the biogas produced is clean, combustible and pollution-free. The technology is simple and appropriate for both rural and urban areas. The utilization of biogas in a farming system may reduce the greenhouse gas, which is responsible for global warming that leads to climate change. In addition, the bio-digested slurry (BDS) can be recommended under organic agriculture. On a large scale, biogas systems may reduce the demand on fossil fuel energy resources and fertilizer cost. The paper reviews the role of biomass anaerobic digestion technology in utilization of biogas as fuel, BDS as fertilizer and other applications in organic agriculture.

Keywords

Anaerobic digestion, Biogas, Biofertilizer, Energy, Sustainable agriculture

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1. Introduction

The production of biogas from cattle dung in a simple and easy to operate unit (biogas plant) is the outcome of research done in India since 1930's. The technology and utilization of biogas as witnessed growing attention as a promising alternative to fossil fuels and providing ecological benefits, conserving natural resources, and minimizing pollution [1]. The per capita energy consumption in India is about 1149 kWh as compared to 10000 kWh in the developed countries. However, the energy scenario in our rural areas is still limited as a result of large demand gap. The non-commercial energy sources such as cattle dung, crop residue, forest waste and firewood contributed more than 89 per cent of energy consumed in rural households that leads to atmospheric pollution and also the heat conversion efficiency is extremely poor [2]. Ultimately, high dependence on firewood for cooking may provide the way for deforestation. Anaerobic digestion (AD) is one of the most sustainable and cost-effective waste treatment technologies for energy recovery in form of biofuels. This process not only reduces the amount of waste, but also transforms biowaste into bioenergy. In addition, the digested biowastes produced during the process are rich in nutrients, which can be used as organic fertilizer in agriculture. This biogas technology converts non-conventional energy into conventional energy. In particular, the gas produced is a clean, combustible and pollution-free. The technology is simple and appropriate for both rural and urban areas [3].

The decay of organic matter, particularly animal and plant wastes, in the absence of air produces an inflammable gas, which consists mainly 55-65 per cent of methane (CH_4) and 34-45 per cent of carbon dioxide (CO_2). The gas is known as biogas and the process is known as anaerobic digestion or fermentation. On the energy side, biogas acts as an efficient domestic fuel that keeps the house and environment clean unlike burning of wood or dung cakes, which is associated with smoke. Biogas used in decentralized system in rural household becomes self-sufficient on domestic energy requirement. On the environmental side, deforestation or cutting of trees for fuel purpose may be reduced.

2. Beneficial applications of anaerobic digestion technology

2.1. Biogas for fuel

Biogas is a mixture of 55 to 65 per cent methane, 35 to 45 per cent carbon dioxide and traces of H_2 , Hydrogen sulphide (H_2S) and ammonia. The possible applications of biogas come under three broad categories, viz heating, lighting and fuel to run the engines. The applications of biogas were depicted in Figure 1. The fuel efficiency of dung is 11 per cent and that of biogas from the same dung is 60 percent. Normally a 3m^3 capacity unit is considered sufficient to meet the heating and lighting needs for a family of 6 to 9 members. The continued dependence of the majority of rural people on biomass

resources for cooking fuel is an issue of concern today. With limited availability of commercial fuels like kerosene and LPG, the dependence on these fuels is likely to increase further in the future. The issue is more difficult to tackle in rural areas because of poor availability and accessibility to commercial fuels, and low purchasing power of majority of the people. Fallout of this situation is that fuel wood is becoming scarce in many parts of the country. As a result, people are forced to switch to inferior fuels such as shrubs, roots and weeds and crop residues. Women are also forced to travel longer distances and spend more time in fuel wood collection. The biogas plant users reported that need for an alternative to traditional fuels; particularly fuel wood is the primary reason for adopting biogas.

2.2. Biogas for cooking and heating appliances

The principle uses of biogas are cooking and lighting. For these two purposes it is not necessary to clean the biogas

- Clean: it does not make dirty cooking vessels, clothes or kitchen.
- Fast: it produces immediate heat.
- Healthy: it does not produce smoke to irritate eyes or lungs
- Efficient: if proper stoves are used.

Figure 1. Applications of biogas as energy source

2.3 Biogas stove

A locally available Janatha kerosene stove is modified into a biogas stove. The kerosene inlet of the stove is permanently closed and a nozzle is provided on the side of the tank. An air hole is also provided on the nozzle with the regulator. The stove wicks are removed and the holes are kept as such for gas entry. The parts above the holes are removed and a flame protection cover made of mild steel sheet is provided to avoid the dissipation of heat.

2.4 Biogas for lighting

There is a big demand for biogas lamps in unelectrified rural areas. Normally the biogas lamps are designed for a gas pressure of 70 to 85 mm water gauge. Low gas pressure gives a poor light and a high gas pressure breaks the mantle quickly. They all are about 100-candle power and use 0.11 to 0.15m³ gas per hour. Any gas lamp with a mantle can use biogas provided a proper air to gas ratio is maintained. Lamps are usually designed to burn gas at minimum pressure of 7.5 cm water column. Gas mantle made of fibre immersed in thorium nitrate solution is reported to give a bright light.

2.5 Portable biogas lamp

Here the biogas is stored in the old lorry or bus tube. A nipple is fitted on the tube to fill the biogas from the biogas plant. It is possible to fill the tube with 140 litres of biogas under normal pressure available in the fixed dome biogas plants. The pressure of 15 cm water column available in the KVIC floating drum type biogas plant is not sufficient to fill the tube. A spring tension arrangement is fixed on the hand. Farmers can use such lamps for irrigating the field and for watch and ward duty, during the night. The gas available in the storage device lasts for 1½ hours for burning the light, and it can be refilled with biogas as and when required.

2.6 Biogas for running engine

Biogas is an excellent fuel for both petrol and diesel engines. The power obtained will be less than that obtained when using liquid fuel alone. Engines using biogas run hotter than on liquid fuel. Therefore, the cooling system needs to be installed in proper condition. Petrol engines can run on 100 per cent methane gas. It is common, however, to use a small quantity of petrol during startup. In diesel engines, the temperature at the end of the compression stroke is usually not over 700°C, whereas the ignition temperature of methane/air mixture is 314°C. Hence the injection of a little diesel fuel just before the end of the compression stroke, to ignite the gas mixture, can ensure the normal running of the engine. To convert the diesel engine to run with biogas, a nipple is attached in the inlet manifold of the engine. The biogas inflow is regulated such that the air-biogas diesel mix will provide optimum performance. The displacement of diesel fuel to the presence of methane takes place through the governor performance which actuates the rack pinion arrangement of the diesel fuel injection system depending on the diesel requirements in accordance with the pressure of biogas this self-regulatory mechanism makes it easy to the engines like Kirlosker without substantially changing the engine design.

For running a 5 HP engine to one hour, the diesel requirement is approximately 1 litre. However, using biogas, engine can run for 5 hours. According to [4] electricity generation capacity of one kWh energy required almost 0.75 m³ gas to run a 100 per cent biogas engine.

3. Bio-digested slurry as fertilizer

Bio-digested slurry (BDS) comes from the anaerobic fermentation of organic matter in a digester having the following characteristics.

3.1. Beneficial effect of BDS on plant nutrients

In the course of biogas fermentation, organic matter will give a large amount of organic acids, which can timely neutralize the ammonia released from organic matter and fix it in the fermentative substrate so as to stop it from escaping. In [5] conducted research on rural biodigesters with same quantity of human and animal excreta put into open manure pits and biogas digesters respectively and then sampled after 30 days of anaerobic digestion. The results showed that the contents of the total N and the ammonia N in slurry is higher in the biogas digester than in the open manure pits respectively. In addition, biodigested slurry has a beneficial effect on the conservation of phosphorous, potassium and other trace elements. The biodigested slurry has different composition in terms of nutrients as compared to open manure due to feed stock types and its mixing ratios. A similar study was conducted by Biogas Development and Training Centre (BDTC), TNAU, Coimbatore, to access the macro nutrient content of various organic manures used for crop production and the results are given in Table 1 [6-8].

Table 1. Macro nutrient composition of manures

S.No	Manure	N ₂ (%)	P ₂ O ₅ (%)	K ₂ O (%)
1.	Fresh cattle dung	0.3 - 0.4	0.1 - 0.2	0.1 - 0.3
2.	Farmyard manure	0.4 - 1.5	0.3 - 0.9	0.3 - 1.9
3.	Compost	0.5 - 1.5	0.3 - 0.9	0.8 - 1.2
4.	Biodigested slurry	1.5 - 2.5	1.0 - 1.5	0.8 - 1.2
5.	Cattle urine	0.9 - 1.2	trace	0.5 - 1.0
6.	Paddy straw	0.3 - 0.4	0.8 - 1.0	0.7 - 0.9
7.	Wheat straw	0.5 - 0.6	0.1 - 0.2	1.1 - 1.3

The results are on par with the results of Culleton et al., (1990). The results clearly indicated that among the various manures evaluated, all the three macro nutrients viz., nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium content were higher in the biodigested slurry which may be due to the decomposition of organic matter in the anaerobic digestion. Long-term application of biodigested slurry is both beneficial to the activity of soil microbes and capable of accelerating the formation of organic and inorganic complexes in soil, thus improving the structure and physicochemical properties of soil. The facts have shown that, the soil in which digested slurry applied had smaller volume weight, bigger porosity, lower compressive strength and larger coefficients of structure and settlement, and is spongy, easy to break and beneficial to cultivation. Accordingly, the application of biogas fertilizer can

be used as an important measure to increase the fertility of soil, improve soil, protect the ecological environment of soil and realize the combination of land use and maintenance. The long-term study also reported that negative effect was observed under organic agriculture with the use of biodigested slurry [9].

3.2. Biodigested slurry - quick acting nutrients

Biogas fertilizer consists of digested slurry and residue. The digested slurry is a quick-acting fertilizer containing many kinds of water-soluble nutrient content and crops are easy to assimilate its nutrient content after it is applied to soil. The digested residue not only contains all-round nutrient elements and organic matter but also adsorbs more effective nutrient contents, hence holding slow-and-quick acting effect concurrently. As a result, it can be said that biogas fertilizer is a fine quality organic fertilizer, which has not only an obvious effect on increase in the yield of current crops but also a noticeable manorial effect on crops.

3.3. Nutrient quality of biogas slurry

When one among eight kinds of feedstock such as pig dung, straws, stalks, etc. was separately fermented in anaerobic gas digester, average consumption of 1 kg dry matter produced 293.3 litres of biogas. Among these materials, pig dung and cattle dung, on the average, lost 50.4% of carbon, 5.6% of nitrogen, 9.3% of phosphorus and 7.2% of potassium. If pig dung and cattle dung were fermented with straws and stalks of crops, the consumption of each kg dry matter generated 409 litres of biogas and on the average, carbon and nitrogen lost 36.9% and 3.8% respectively, but potassium and phosphorus were basically the same [10]. This indicates that the mixed fermentation of different types of feedstocks can not only increase the yield of biogas, but also decrease the loss of nutrients in biogas fertilizer and enhance the quality of fertilizer.

4. Other application of bio digested sludge in organic agriculture

4.1. Biodigested sludge waste for *Chlorella* cultivation

Solid portion is recovered from the sludge and remaining liquid portion may be considered as important source of nutrients which may be act as growth promoter of algae. Algae are primitive plants, including the seaweeds and the green scum which are living in fresh water ponds. The most algae consist chlorophyll, which enables synthesis their own food in the presence of sunlight. There are more than 20,000 known species of algae available across the globe. However, *Chlorella* can be found to be suitable option for biogas slurry [11-13]. *Chlorella* is a single-celled high protein algae. *Chlorella* consists of 36 to 40 per cent of protein, which makes a good protein supplement for animals.

The liquid portion of the sludge can be used to grow *chlorella* in shallow ponds. The pond should be lined with concrete, metal or plastic material to avoid contamination and make harvesting easier. In organic agriculture, polyethylene may be used instead of plastic materials. Likewise, plastics made with polychloride based products will be restricted in organic agriculture.

Chlorella is harvested early in the morning before sunrise. The water can be drained out and the *chlorella* is then scraped off. It is harvested 6 to 7 days after the inoculation with a *chlorella*. *Chlorella* can be used as animal feed at the ratio of up to 10 per cent that replaced the soybean oil meal for protein supplementation. However, at present cost of soybean oil meal, large-scale commercial production of *chlorella* is not economically viable. In addition, the harvesting and drying processes under *Chlorella* cultivation is labor intensive.

4.2. Biodigested slurry used as feed in fishponds

The basic source of feed for fish is the plankton, the huge number of small plants and animals found near the surface of bodies of water. The plant population of plankton consists mainly of algae. The animal population consists of many kinds of single-celled organism, crustaceans and the larvae form of other animals. In general, Poultry and livestock manures are directly used in fishponds to grow phytoplankton. However, odor produced by the plankton may have adverse effect on palatability of fish. This is particularly evident in the case of bangus (milk fish) type fish. The optional way is to pass the manure through a biogas plant and use the resulting sludge in the fishpond. The advantages of this method include,

- The sludge is not odorous and will not adversely affect the palatability of the fish.
- The sludge promotes the growth of the plankton as compared to fresh manure.
- The sludge has a lower biological oxygen demand (BOD) than fresh manure slurry, thus leaving more oxygen available for fish in the fishpond.

5. Conclusion

According to available research on biogas activities, in terms of commercial energy and fertilizer equivalents, it may be assumed that, biogas technology is usually less costly as compared to other energy and fertilizer sources. Likewise, use of biogas in a farming system may reduce the greenhouse gas, which is responsible for global warming that leads to climate change.

Hence, the widespread use of biogas systems would therefore be recommended to reduce the demand on fossil fuel energy resources and fertilizer cost. Similarly, countries like India have natural resources depletion occurring at a faster rate. Therefore, biogas technology can be a suitable option in one-way that produce energy and in other way that minimize the

greenhouse gas accumulation in the atmosphere. In addition, the biogas digested slurry can be recommended under organic agriculture. However, proper certification should be carried out based on the regulation of certification agency.

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